

IEEE Xplore

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("Full Text & Metadata":"resistor*" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"resistive" OR
"Full Text & Metadata":"resistor network" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"we-delta"
OR "Full Text & Metadata":"resistance" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"thick*film" OR
"Full Text & Metadata":"thin*film" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"wirewound" OR
"Full Text & Metadata":"metal foil" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"bulk resistor*"
OR "Full Text & Metadata":"carbon resistor*" OR "Full Text &
Metadata":"resistive device" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"composition resistor*"
OR "Full Text & Metadata":"carbon film resistor*" OR "Full Text &
Metadata":"metal oxide resistor*") AND ("Full Text & Metadata":"excess noise" OR
"Full Text & Metadata":"current noise" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"voltage noise"
OR "Full Text & Metadata":"1/f noise" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"low-frequency
noise" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"electrical noise" OR "Full Text &
Metadata":"white noise" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"pink noise" OR "Full Text &
Metadata":"johnson noise" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"flicker noise" OR "Full
Text & Metadata":"thermal noise" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"shot noise" OR "Full
Text & Metadata":"resistance fluctuations" OR "Full Text &
Metadata":"stochastic noise" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"gaussian noise" OR "Full
Text & Metadata":"electromagnetic noise") AND ("Full Text & Metadata":"noise
measurement" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"noise analysis" OR "Full Text &
Metadata":"noise characterization" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"methods" OR "Full
Text & Metadata":"analysis" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"test system" OR "Full
Text & Metadata":"bridge method" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"noise spectral
density" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"noise spectra") AND ("Full Text &
Metadata":"noise mitigation" OR "Full Text & Metadata":"noise index" OR "Full
Text & Metadata":"low frequency noise contribution")
```

Advanced Search, Command Search - colar o texto completo da pesquisa ou
Advanced search colar cada string P/I/C/O de busca tirando os parênteses inicial
e final em cada search term e selecionar em cada um deles a a opção Full Text &
Metadata

Scopus

```
("resistor*" OR "resistive" OR "resistor network" OR "we-delta" OR "resistance"
OR "thick*film" OR "thin*film" OR "wirewound" OR "metal foil" OR "bulk
resistor*" OR "carbon resistor*" OR "resistive device" OR "composition
resistor*" OR "carbon film resistor*" OR "metal oxide resistor*")AND("excess
noise" OR "current noise" OR "voltage noise" OR "1/f noise" OR "low-frequency
noise" OR "electrical noise" OR "white noise" OR "pink noise" OR "johnson noise"
OR "flicker noise" OR "thermal noise" OR "shot noise" OR "resistance
fluctuations" OR "stochastic noise" OR "gaussian noise" OR "electromagnetic
noise") AND ("noise measurement" OR "noise analysis" OR "noise characterization"
OR "methods" OR "analysis" OR "test system" OR "bridge method" OR "noise
spectral density" OR "noise spectra") AND ("noise mitigation" OR "noise index"
OR "low frequency noise contribution")
```

Acessar com um computador no Inmetro, logar e depois ir em "search documents" e
colar a string completa de busca, selecionar search within "All Fields"

<https://www-scopus-com.ez306.periodicos.capes.gov.br/search/form.uri?display=advanced>

SpringerLink

("resistor*" OR "resistive" OR "resistor network" OR "weye-delta" OR "resistance" OR "thick*film" OR "thin*film" OR "wirewound" OR "metal foil" OR "bulk resistor*" OR "carbon resistor*" OR "resistive device" OR "composition resistor*" OR "carbon film resistor*" OR "metal oxide resistor*") AND ("excess noise" OR "current noise" OR "voltage noise" OR "1/f noise" OR "low-frequency noise" OR "electrical noise" OR "white noise" OR "pink noise" OR "johnson noise" OR "flicker noise" OR "thermal noise" OR "shot noise" OR "resistance fluctuations" OR "stochastic noise" OR "gaussian noise" OR "eletromagnetic noise") AND ("noise measurement" OR "noise analysis" OR "noise characterization" OR "methods" OR "analysis" OR "test system" OR "bridge method" OR "noise spectral density" OR "noise spectra") AND ("noise mitigation" OR "noise index" OR "low frequency noise contribution")

Acessar com um computador no Inmetro, depois ir em "search for articles, journals, books, authors, videos" e colar a string completa de busca

Web of Science

("resistor*" OR "resistive" OR "resistor network" OR "weye-delta" OR "resistance" OR "thick*film" OR "thin*film" OR "wirewound" OR "metal foil" OR "bulk resistor*" OR "carbon resistor*" OR "resistive device" OR "composition resistor*" OR "carbon film resistor*" OR "metal oxide resistor*")AND("excess noise" OR "current noise" OR "voltage noise" OR "1/f noise" OR "low-frequency noise" OR "electrical noise" OR "white noise" OR "pink noise" OR "johnson noise" OR "flicker noise" OR "thermal noise" OR "shot noise" OR "resistance fluctuations" OR "stochastic noise" OR "gaussian noise" OR "eletromagnetic noise") AND ("noise measurement" OR "noise analysis" OR "noise characterization" OR "methods" OR "analysis" OR "test system" OR "bridge method" OR "noise spectral density" OR "noise spectra") AND ("noise mitigation" OR "noise index" OR "low frequency noise contribution")

Ir em "Advanced Search", selecionar "Documents", Search in: Web of Science Core Collection, Editions: All e colar a string completa de busca onde mostra example: Onde mostra "Topic" selecionar a opção "All Fields"

Scispace

Pergunta de pesquisa usada:

What types of electrical noise are present in resistors and resistive networks, and how are these noises characterized?

<https://scispace.com/search?q=What+types+of+electrical+noise+are+present+in+resistors+and+resistive+networks%2C+and+how+are+these+noises+characterized%3F>